

WHY WE NEED CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT ON OUR CLASS?!

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Classroom management refers to the wide variety of skills and techniques that teachers use to keep students organized, orderly, focused, attentive, on task, and academically productive during a class. When classroom-management strategies are executed effectively, teachers minimize the behaviors that impede learning for both individual students and groups of students, while maximizing the behaviors that facilitate or enhance learning. Generally speaking, effective teachers tend to display strong classroom-management skills, while the hallmark of the inexperienced or less effective teacher is a disorderly classroom filled with students who are not working or paying attention.

It's important to note that no teacher will constantly fit into just one category. Students are all unique, and different situations call for different practices. However, researchers have determined that the closer a teacher is to an authoritative approach, the greater the impact they'll have on their students. Classroom management is the most important aspect of a successful classroom, but finding the right balance of control and involvement takes some trial-and-error.

If you're a new teacher, take your time to figure out what works best for you. Try different classroom management strategies and see how they impact your students. Then, ask yourself if the strategy impacts student outcomes positively or negatively. Once you have answered that question, pivot your approach as needed until you find the right balance.

On the other hand, if you are a more experienced teacher, be sure to take the time to reflect on your classroom management style and adjust it as needed. Many teachers don't intentionally choose to be permissive or indulgent, but rather their decisions lead them to lose control of their classroom. Don't let yourself get stuck in your ways with the wrong approach. It's never too late to change your teaching style to better serve your students!

This also ensures that all teachers strive towards a well-defined standard of teaching and engaging with students. Broadly speaking, there are four styles of classroom management:

These styles range from very strong teacher control with minimal student involvement to lose teacher control with maximal student involvement. In this blog, we are sketching out each of these styles with their pros and cons, so that you can make an informed decision on which style you want to incorporate in your school.

1. Authoritarian

The authoritarian classroom management style is basically a style where the teacher has complete control over the classroom. Students are not actively involved or responsive. In this strictest form of class management style, it is quite likely that a student not following the set rules can be punished. There is no scope for friendly student-teacher relationships in this overly structured style. In this classroom management style, there is no student autonomy in deciding how they will learn, collaborate with their peers, or how they will engage in class.

It is observed however that the majority of students perform better if they collaborate with their peers and have some kind of classroom involvement. This makes student's feel accepted, heard, cared for and promotes a feeling of safety inside the classroom. Furthermore, a positive relationship with their teacher encourages students to reach their full potential.

An authoritarian structure might make you feel that things are under control, but it can become counterproductive and hinder your students' growth. Unless there is any strong reason, you should avoid having an authoritarian classroom management system at your school.

2. Authoritative

The authoritative classroom management style aims to strike a balance between teacher control and student involvement. Students are encouraged to participate in the class and collaborate with their peers, while all the time following set

rules. Student inputs and feedback are valued by teachers and actively worked upon to make learning a better experience for students.

In general, student outcomes in an authoritative classroom management style are positive, and usually, students show growth in all areas.

3. Permissive

Permissive classroom management style has both low levels of control as well as student involvement. The students are pretty much left to themselves to do as they please. This primarily arises due to the lack of structure and planning from the teachers and the school management.

With low control levels coupled with low involvement levels, only a few students manage to do well. In this setting, students' educational fate is unpredictable. Left to chance, the students may never get enough opportunities and guidance to make the fullest of their potential.

4. Indulgent

Indulgent classroom management style involves a high level of involvement with a low level of control. Students have the freedom to express themselves freely in the classroom and can collaborate with their peers. Teachers using this style are usually very well-liked by the students. However, there is a real danger of the classroom accomplishing nothing in the set time due to the lack of control.

Student outcomes in this setting must be understood in a dual manner: When students feel free enough to interact with their teacher, they feel safe and well cared for. However, to make this style work, there has to be some kind of control over the students. Teachers adopting this style often end up unable to finish subject portions in due time.

It's important to note that no teacher will constantly fit into just one category. Students are all unique, and different situations call for different practices. However, researchers have determined that the closer a teacher is to an authoritative approach, the greater the impact they'll have on their students. Classroom management is the most important aspect of a successful classroom, but finding the right balance of control and involvement takes some trial-and-error.

It is important to drive the appropriate classroom management style at your school rather than leaving it up to the teachers. To do so, you should involve the parents and teachers alike to understand their opinions. A well-defined classroom management style must be communicated to teachers in their training program itself. These four styles represent extremes, and most teachers demonstrate a certain degree of inconsistency in their use of styles.

Research has shown that the type of management style used results in characteristic behaviors.

- The authoritative style helps to produce students who are socially competent and responsible.
- The authoritarian style helps to produce students who are ineffective at social interaction, and somewhat inactive.
- Both indulgent and permissive styles help to produce students that are immature, show poor self-restraint, and who exhibit poor leadership skills.

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On the other hand, if you are a more experienced teacher, be sure to take the time to reflect on your classroom management style and adjust it as needed. Many teachers don't intentionally choose to be permissive or indulgent, but rather their decisions lead them to lose control of their classroom. Don't let yourself get stuck in your ways with the wrong approach. It's never too late to change your teaching style to better serve your students!

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